

Coping with the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Plight of Urban Slum Dwellers in Kolkata, India

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Abstract

We analysed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on slum dwellers in Kolkata, West Bengal, using a primary questionnaire-based survey and time use survey of the head of the household and his or her spouse from 252 households, with a total of 504 respondents. The unconditional quantile regression analysis shows that the monthly household income didn't change significantly during the pre- and post-COVID-19 periods even though there was a slight decrease in the income of male slum dwellers in the post-pandemic period. Second, women's full-time and part-time employment increased in the post COVID-19 period compared to the pre-COVID-19 era, because women who had not worked prior to the pandemic joined the labour force to maintain their monthly household income. We also conceptualized the "Me-Time" concept, which is the sum of time spent on leisure and sleeping. We used a 70% percent median me-time in the sample data as a threshold for the time poverty line during the post-COVID-19 period. Our findings show that me-time is 48 minutes and 88 minutes less, respectively, for fully employed or partially employed women, compared to their male counterparts. The number of children under 10 years significantly reduces an individual me-time across all employment status subgroups. We also used a time poverty threshold based on the committed time of the respondents, where the threshold is defined as 1.5 times the median committed time in the sample. We observe that 25% of fully employed women are time poor, compared to only 8.3% of fully employed men.

Keywords

COVID-19 pandemic, income, time poverty, employment status, gender

JEL codes: I3, J16, O18, E24

Introduction

The present paper has undertaken a primary survey to identify the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic if any on the employment status and household income of urban slum dwellers. We also measured time poverty among male and female respondents from urban slum areas in Kolkata, West Bengal. We all know that the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has been a hard-hitting experience for underprivileged people in India with slum dwellers being no exception. Biswas (2020) notes that in the city of Kolkata, which has a high population density, around 32% of the city population dwell in slum areas with even higher population density. The pandemic has actually intensified vulnerability of slum dwellers (Biswas 2020; Ghosh et al. 2020; Auerbach and Thachil 2021) who are challenged with over-crowding coupled with the lack of civic amenities and shared toilet facilities (UN-Habitat 2021). As a result, social distancing and continuous hand washing were almost impossible to achieve in slum areas (Roy and Chatterji 2021). A study in the context of Mumbai shows that urban poor has become the ultimate victim of the socioeconomic crisis caused by social distancing and lockdown measures to combat the COVID-19 infection rate (Bhattacharjee and Sattar 2022). Another study (Das et al. 2021) identified that slums located in the eastern and central parts of India (particularly Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Odisha, West Bengal) were more vulnerable to COVID-19 transmission due to lack of availability as well as accessibility of basic services and amenities to slum dwellers. Job loss¹ in urban informal sectors was another crucial impact of the pandemic, leading to a spike in the unemployment rate (Roy and Chatterji 2021). Roy and Chatterji (2021) further state that urban informal workers like drivers of auto-rickshaws, rickshaw pullers, street vendors, labourers from construction projects lost their employment during the pandemic. It has been noted that the pandemic had a severe impact on wage workers in the informal sector in urban areas in India, including women, scheduled castes (the Dalits) and religious minorities (notably Muslims) (Dang et al. 2021). Similar results have been also found in various slums in two Indian cities namely Bengaluru and Patna (Downs-Tepper et al. 2022). Research using the CMIE Consumer Pyramids Household Survey shows that incomes of wage workers dropped by 35%, while incomes of daily labourers – by 75% (Gupta et al. 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic containment measures (lockdown) on employment have affected the livelihood and food security of households as evident from large-scale survey data on about 5000 respondents across 12 states of India, conducted from April to May 2020 (Kesar et al. 2021). The income decline has led to a reduction in the consumption of basic commodities, including food grains, and an increase in debt (Kesar et al. 2021). A survey of 3000 households in the national capital region around Delhi shows that the urban informal workforce, which is mainly outside the social security network, has been extremely affected by the lockdown measures due to reductions in income and livelihood (Choudhuri et al. 2023). A telephone survey conducted in four cities of India revealed that 83% of its participants experienced difficulties accessing health care, while 17% faced difficulties accessing medicines, 59% reported a loss of income, 38% – a loss of employment, and 28% reduced their consumption of fruit and vegetables (Singh et al. 2021).

1 Centre for Monitoring of Indian Economy observed that the COVID pandemic lockdown caused a 122 million job losses. Source: Coronavirus lockdown: India jobless numbers cross 120 million in April. URL: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-52559324>.

Thus, the above studies have investigated the immediate impact of the pandemic. Our objective is to observe how the respondents cope with the shock and resume economic activities after the pandemic. To do so, we will compare the pre- and post-pandemic income and employment status of Kolkata slum males and female. This will help us to understand how well slum dwellers have managed to cope with the pandemic situation over time.

Various studies on Indian slum dwellers have raised several interesting issues. In general, Indian slums are characterised by a high population density with crowded living conditions, shared toilets, a lack of proper sanitation, sewerage and waste management systems, and sometimes a lack of access to clean drinking water (Edelman and Mitra 2006; Sajjad 2014; Chimankar 2016; Mawkhlieng and Debbarma 2018). Bag and Seth (2018) demonstrate that higher levels of living standards measured through a monetary approach may not correlate with the measures obtained through non-monetary approaches for slum dwellers in Mumbai, Kolkata and Delhi. Another study by Ray (2017) based on 200 samples from selected slums in Kolkata found that slum dwellers were mostly employed in the informal sector with an average monthly income of around Rs. 12000. This study showed that poor housing and sanitation facilities led to a poor quality of life. However, the study also found that the accessibility and affordability of education to slum dwellers was a challenge as well as availability of recreational activities. Edelman and Mitra (2006) noted the continued vulnerability of slum dwellers, using data from the Slum Survey (2004-2005). They observed that slum residents used political connections as a survival strategy to get access to basic amenities.

The existing policy framework on slum dwellers in India fails to acknowledge the basic needs of people residing in slum areas, where the slums are offshoots of rapid urbanisation, leading to a high rural-urban migration. Various studies have pointed out that slum dwellers are mostly employed in the urban informal sector (Roy and Chatterji 2021). Given this situation, the government of India has implemented various strategies aimed at slum dwellers over time. From independence until the middle of the 1960s, policies were focused on removing, demolishing and clearing slums out of cities, (Mitra 2021; Chowdhury and Samanta 2024) as slums were considered an obstacle to urban development. Andavarapu and Edelman (2013) noted that between 1950 and 1972, policies were implemented to demolish slums and rehabilitate slum dwellers in apartment-type public housing in the suburbs of cities. The next phase, from the mid-1960s to the 1990s, witnessed a shift in the policy objectives, with a focus on the upgrade and improvement of slums and quality of life of the residents (Andavarapu and Edelman 2013; Chatterjee 2020; Mitra 2021; Chowdhury and Samanta 2024). In the post liberalisation period, starting from 1991, several initiatives have been undertaken to develop housing in slum areas with various social schemes, including Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission (JNNURM 2005), Rajiv Awas Yojana (RAY 2011), Pradhan Mantri Awa Yojana–Urban (PMAY-U 2015), Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM 2014), and Jal Jeevan Mission-Urban (JJM Urban 2021). Policies like PMAY-U coupled with SBM, concentrated on in-situ housing development with better access to drinking water and sanitation and sewerage systems. However, most of these policies have had a limited effect, as in-situ housing development failed to address the problem of overcrowded living conditions in slums.

Given this background, the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the Indian slum dwellers in two ways: first, the implementation of social distancing and sanitisation

practices turned out to be hardly possible under overcrowded living conditions, increasing the risk of infection; and second, a huge number of slum dwellers has lost employment in the urban informal sector. During this period, the government of India under the leadership of Prime Minister Garib Kalyan, implemented the Anna Yojana programme (Phase I and II)², providing free food grains to millions of people. In our survey area of Kolkata, the government of West Bengal has also distributed free food grains through its enhanced public distribution system³. Even though the food security was provided through different safety nets, other needs, including medical ones, child care, and pre-natal care for pregnant women were not fully addressed for those who had lost their livelihood⁴ due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

In view of the extreme sufferings of slum dwellers in the pandemic period, we have undertaken this study to better understand their resilience in the face of this shock. In addition to comparing their pre- and post-pandemic income levels and employment status, we also conducted a time-use survey to measure the time poverty of household heads and their spouses during the post-pandemic period, as time poverty has serious health and psychological consequences, leading to a low productivity, lack of human capital accumulation, and low well-being. Based on our review of the existing literature, we have identified two possible areas where our study could contribute to the field.

First, we would like to emphasise that the majority of the reviewed papers on the impact of the pandemic on lives and livelihoods of poor urban people are mostly concentrated on the immediate effects of the pandemic. Our objective is different. We surveyed a group of urban slum dwellers from April to December 2023, to understand the change in their income and employment just after the pandemic, compared to their pre-COVID income and employment status. The pre-COVID information has been collected using recall method during the primary survey.

Second, we have found that none of the studies within the Indian context measures the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the time use patterns of slum dwellers. In this context we are looking at the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on employment, household income, and subsequently on time poverty of slum dwellers. Additionally, we will explore the extent of time poverty in relation to income poverty. Our study aims to fill this gap in the literature by connecting the issue of time poverty with income poverty of individuals living in urban slums in Kolkata.

This study will contribute to the existing literature in the following way. First, we will estimate how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected household income, employment status and individual income. The analysis will be conducted separately for male and female participants of the survey.

Second, we will determine the incidence, depth and severity of time poverty based on the time-use survey. Then, we will try to relate time poverty to income poverty using explorato-

2 India's Food Security Response to COVID-19. How India Fed 810 Million Poor and Migrants in the Pandemic (2021) URL: <https://www.microsave.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Indias-food-security-response-to-COVID-19.pdf>

3 Bengal food crisis in COVID lockdown saved by Mamata Banerjee's free distribution of food grains. URL: <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/bengal-food-crisis-in-covid-lockdown-saved-by-mamata-banerjee-s-free-distribution-of-food-grains-report-11656669534288.html>

4 Staying Alive: COVID-19 and Public Services in West Bengal. URL: <https://ruralindiaonline.org/or/library/resource/staying-alive-covid-19-and-public-services-in-west-bengal/>

ry analysis in the context of urban slums in Kolkata, West Bengal, which we have not seen in the literature.

Third, we will attempt to identify a possible impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on time-poverty.

Finally, this study is also expected to assist us in identifying the presence and extent of intra-household disparities in time use patterns among urban slum dwellers in Kolkata.

Material and Methods

We have conducted our primary survey and time-use survey in “Pyara Bagan Bustee”, a slum area located at 39B Beltala Road in Kolkata, 700020, ward 69 of Kolkata Municipal Corporation in West Bengal. The area is surrounded by Beltala Road, Sarat Bose road, Ballygaunge circular Road. The study by Mishra et al. (2013) provides a detailed description of this slum. According to the study by Mishra et al. (2013), this particular slum is an informal settlement that is 150 years old and covers four acres of land. It is inhabited by around twelve thousand people as of 2013. As this is one of the largest slums in the South Kolkata area, we have carried out our survey in this area. We used the method of systematic sampling and surveyed every 5th dweller from the narrow lanes of the slum, starting from the right-hand side. We surveyed married couples (both husband and wife) to understand the intrahousehold disparities in time poverty among the subjects⁵. We surveyed 252 households. From each household we interviewed both the main earner and his/her spouse, resulting in a total of 504 respondents. During the socio-demographic survey, we elicited information on age of the respondents, marriage duration, age at first childbirth (if any), number of living children and their gender, date of last childbirth, years of schooling, religion, caste, type of family, housing conditions, toilet, drinking water facilities, health conditions, COVID-19 vaccination information, information on holding a bank account, information on loans for both the main earner and his/her spouse. We also collected information on income and employment status during the pre- and post-COVID-19 periods for both the main earner and his/her spouse. To track the present level of individual and household income and employment status, we asked them to report their income and employment status as of one month just prior to the date of the survey. To collect data on the pre-COVID-19 pandemic period, we used 25th of March 2020, as the cut-off date, as on that date the nation-wide lockdown was initiated in India. We asked the respondents to recall their income and employment status as of one month prior to March, 25, 2020. From female respondents, we collected information on decision-making autonomy, spousal violence and alcoholism of husband. The time-use survey extracted information on various activities performed by each respondent during a 24-hour period with a 30-minute time interval. In the case of multi-tasking activities, activities are classified as primary, secondary or tertiary. Tables 1 and 2 describe the sample.

5 Our survey included only married couples as our initial objective was to understand the intra-household gender differences between spouses in income and time commitments. Hence, we excluded households with single male/female separated/divorced/ or widowed.

Table 1. Summary statistics of demographic variables

Indicators	percentage
Below Poverty Level (BPL) card holder (%)	67.8
General (%)	84.92
Scheduled Caste (%)	13.89
Scheduled Tribe (%)	4
Other Backward Case (%)	7.9
Female Principal earner (%)	11.9
Average Household Size	4.424
N = 252	

Source: Authors' own calculation

Table 2. Income and employment during the pre- and post-COVID pandemic period

	Pre-COVID N = 252	Post-COVID N = 252
Average Monthly Income in Rs. (Overall)	11574.6	11756.74
Average Monthly Income in Rs. (Male)	8366.667	7999.996
Average Monthly Income in Rs. (Female)	3207.937	3756.746
Full time employment (Overall %)	68.06	70.24
Full time employment (Male %)	95.65	91.27
Full time employment (Female %)	42.46	49.21
Part time employment (Overall %)	15.28	20.63
Part time employment (Male %)	3.17	3.97
Part time employment (Female %)	27.38	37.30
Unemployed (Overall %)	16.67	9.13
Unemployed (Male %)	3.17	4.76
Unemployed (Female %)	30.16	13.49

Source: Authors' own calculation. Note: The mean difference in average monthly income during the pre- and post-COVID periods is insignificant for overall and male groups and significant for female sub-group at 1% level.

Methodology for Data Analysis

Effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on household and individual income

Quantile regression is a methodology of tracing the linear association between different quantiles of the outcome/dependent variables with a set of control variables. The conditional quantile regression model was developed to estimate the linear dependency between conditional quantiles of the outcome variable to the set of covariates (Koenker and Bassett

1978). However, a limitation of this methodology is that the estimated conditional quantiles are not robust to change in the distribution of explanatory variables. In the present context, we apply unconditional quantiles for the pre- and post-COVID-19 pandemic periods for individual/household income to observe the shift in the distribution of income over time (Firpo et al. 2009). Let I be a vector of the observed earned income of individuals with the presence of a set of covariates X . We assume that I and X have joint distribution. Let H be an unconditional distribution function of I . We measure the influence of a small increase in the location of the distribution of the explanatory variable X on the τ th quantile of the unconditional distribution Q_τ of I . The study used unconditional quantile regression (UQR), applying an Influence Function (IF) and Re-centred Influence function (RIF). The IF assesses the impact (or ‘influence’) of removing/adding an observation to the value of a statistic (say Q_τ), without having to recalculate that statistic (Borah and Basu 2013).

The Re-centered Influence Function (RIF) is found by adding the statistic to its IF. The RIF of the dependent variable, used extensively in a robust estimation (Fang and Sakellariou 2016) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RIF}(I, Q_\tau) &= Q_\tau + \text{IF}(I, Q_\tau), \\ \text{RIF}(I, Q_\tau) &= Q_\tau + \frac{\tau - k(I \leq Q_\tau)}{f_I(Q_\tau)}. \end{aligned}$$

Here Q_τ is the τ th quantile of the unconditional distribution of I . The probability density function of the variable I evaluated at Q_τ is $f_I(Q_\tau)$. The indicator variable $k(I \leq Q_\tau)$ shows whether the outcome value is less than Q_τ or not. Next, the equation takes into account the impact of an observation on a specific distributional statistic, say, Q_τ . If the conditional expectation of $\text{RIF}(I; Q_\tau)$ is conceptualised as a function of explanatory variables, the RIF regression can be viewed as a UQR.

$$E\{\text{RIF}(I, Q_\tau) \mid X\} = X\gamma_\tau.$$

In our case, we have information about the income of 504 respondents in the pre- and post-COVID periods. Thus, we have 1008 data points on household income and individual income. The explanatory variables used in the analysis are: COVID-dummy, which is zero for the period before the pandemic and one otherwise; age of the respondent; square of age of the respondent before and after the COVID period; and size of the household before and after COVID-19. Other household-level variables included whether the household belonged to the below poverty level category (BPL) and the bank account holding status, as well as years of education of the respondent. These three variables were the same for both the post- and pre-pandemic periods. We estimated the unconditional income quartiles using robust standard errors for both pre- and post-pandemic levels of individual income to compare possible changes.

Determinants of employment status

To identify a set of variables influencing the employment status and impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, we used a heteroscedasticity corrected multinomial probit regression model. The employment status variable has the following three categories: unemployed, full-time employed and part-time employed. Therefore, we apply multinomial probit regression. Multinomial probit regression often assumes that there is one latent variable for each category of the outcome variable. Let the latent variable for the j th alternative, where

$j = 1, 2, 3 \dots J$, be $u_{ij} = \beta_j x_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$ where x_i is the vector of the observed independent variables for the i th individual. Here $\varepsilon_{i1}, \varepsilon_{i2} \dots \varepsilon_{ij}$ are error terms distributed independently and identically to the standard normal distribution. The decision maker chooses the alternative r such that $u_{ir} > u_{im}$ for $r \neq m$.

Suppose, an individual I chooses k . Let $v_{ijk} = u_{ij} - u_{ik}$ for $j = 1, 2, 3 \dots J$.

Let $\xi_{il} = \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ik}$ where $l = j$ if $j < k$ and $l = j - 1$, such that $l = 1, 2, \dots J - 1$.

$Var(\xi_{il}) = Var(\varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ik}) = 2$, $Cov(\xi_{il}, \xi_{il'}) = 1$.

$Prob[I \text{ chooses } k] = Prob[v_{i1k} \leq 0, v_{i2k} \leq 0, \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots v_{iJ-1k} \leq 0]$.

Thus, the likelihood function involves computing probabilities from the multivariate normal distribution. In this case we also have pre- and post-COVID data on 504 respondents, totalling 1008 data points. Here our x_i vector contains a COVID-dummy, pre- and post-pandemic levels of the number of children under 10 years and pre- and post-pandemic age of the respondent, and square of the age of the respondent. Also, we included gender of the sample, if belongs to below poverty level category (BPL), bank account holding status and years of education of the respondent, which remained the same for both pre- and post-pandemic periods.

Determinants of male/female time poverty gap

Multiple regression analysis is used to isolate the determinants of the time poverty gap between males and females. The heteroscedasticity-corrected ordinary least square method estimates the gender-specific time poverty gap among fully employed, part-time employed, and unemployed groups. The regression equation used is as follows:

$$Ti = a + bx_i + ui.$$

Where T is discretionary time (in minutes) and x is a vector of variables such as gender, age, age-square, number of children under 10 years, holding of a bank account, years of schooling and below poverty line (BPL) dummy. u is a random error term.

Time-poverty measurement. Committed time is the total amount of time spent on market activities, household activities, care activities, and shopping. On the other hand, we define “Me-time” as the total time spent on leisure and sleeping. We defined two different thresholds for time poverty, one based on committed time and other based on me-time. Following the existing literature, 70 percent of the median me-time in the sample data was used as one threshold for the time-poverty line. In our analysis, we have used 455 minutes as a critical me-time poverty line. Any individual who enjoys less than this critical level of me-time is considered to be time poor. Secondly, according to the Indian labour law, 8 hours or 480 minutes, is the labour day or working hours per day. However, if a person works more than 1.5 times that amount, that is, 720 minutes per day, we use it as a critical poverty line for measuring committed time poverty. A person is considered to be time-poor if their committed time exceeds 720 minutes or if their discretionary time is less than 455 minutes a day.

Calculation of time poverty indices. As a poverty index, we used a modified Foster Greer Thorbeck Indices (FGT), a class of poverty indices for measuring depth, severity and incidence of time-poverty across different socio-economic-demographic groups. The FGT index of order zero measures the headcount ratio (HCR). The order one FGT index indicates the average poverty gap, and the order two FGT index captures the severity of time poverty.

FGT formula when x is the committed time (in minutes):

$$FGT(\alpha) = \frac{\sum x_j > x \cdot (x_j - x_{j^*})^\alpha}{n(x_{j^*})^\alpha} \tag{1}$$

FGT formula when x indicates me-time (in minutes):

$$FGT(\alpha) = \frac{\sum x_j < x \cdot (x_{j^*} - x_j)^\alpha}{n(x_{j^*})^\alpha} \tag{1'}$$

Where x_{j^*} is the time poverty line. For $\alpha = 0$, equation (1) provides HCR; for $\alpha = 1$, it gives the depth and for $\alpha = 2$, it provides the severity of poverty. It should be noted that we have used the FGT class of indices with a slight modification of the definition.

Results and Discussion

Table 3 outlines the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on household income.

Tables 3. Unconditional quantile regression for first quartile, median and third quartile for monthly household income of the respondents from the slum area in Kolkata, India

Dependent Variable: Household_income	Distributional Statistic: q(25)	Distributional Statistic: q(50)	Distributional Statistic: q(75)
	Coef. (Robust Standard Error)		
Covid dummy	178.0729 (204.1826)	269.4862 (231.35)	175.3031 (310.2389)
BPL Dummy	436.428* (224.8501)	1358.051*** (254.3536)	1832.936*** (317.9883)
Household size	-158.8407** (67.62244)	-42.85476 (78.6075)	78.24239 (108.812)
Age	-24.03537 (90.23115)	190.3045* (100.3302)	400.9613*** (129.7509)
Age-Square	0.337885 (1.230996)	-2.012195 (1.322516)	-4.02366** (1.753672)
Bank account dummy	687.0606** (296.6822)	725.9952** (310.0372)	556.8398 (400.7226)
Years of schooling	140.036*** (30.8854)	103.9367*** (33.66148)	92.36285** (43.91032)
Constant	8992.367 (1669.2)	5120.435 (1909.156)	1751.193 (2436.07)
Estimated quartile	9801.3	11434	13570
Number of obs	1008	1008	1008

Dependent Variable: Household_income	Distributional Statistic: q(25)	Distributional Statistic: q(50)	Distributional Statistic: q(75)
	Coef. (Robust Standard Error)		
F(8, 999)	6.78	7.39	11.87
Prob > F	0.0000	0.00	0.00
R-squared	0.0407	0.0473	0.0634
Root MSE	3241.3	3672.6	4924.9

Source: Authors’ estimation based on the survey data. Note: *** p < .01; ** p < .05; *p < .1.

Figure 1. Distribution of household income during the pre- and post- pandemic periods based on unconditional quantile regressions for the respondents from the slum area in Kolkata, India. Source: Authors’ drawing based on estimation from unconditional quantile regressions. (Regression results are available upon request from the authors)

In our slum survey, Table 3 and figure 1 clearly show that after the pandemic, when we collected data in 2023, the households were able to recover their monthly income almost up to the post-pandemic level. Also, BPL status and years of education have a positive significant impact on all quantiles.

Now we will analyse changes in the level of individual income using Table 4 and Figure 2, which are based on unconditional quantile regression, with the control for variables below poverty level category (BPL), number of children under 10 years, age of the respondent, square of the age of the respondent, bank account holding status and years of schooling.

Table 4 shows that the COVID dummy variable is negatively significant at 10% level for males in the median regression. However, it is positively significant for females at 1% level for the first quartile and the median. Figure 2 further illustrates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on individual income.

Table 4. Unconditional quantile regression for first quartile, median and third quartile for monthly income of male and female respondents from the slum area in Kolkata, India

Individual income	Male Respondents			Female Respondents		
	Distributional Statistic: q(25)	Distributional Statistic: q(50)	Distributional Statistic: q(75)	Distributional Statistic: q(25)	Distributional Statistic: q(50)	Distributional Statistic: q(75)
	Coef. (Robust Standard Error)					
Covid dummy	-335.073 (282.1521)	-555.673* (303.1802)	-292.446 (370.5174)	1662.013*** (359.3803)	770.762*** (262.5148)	331.5664 (367.9798)
BPL dummy	-201.679 (284.5534)	440.0108 (337.1038)	405.4904 (404.8688)	1897.039*** (435.4698)	1843.028*** (299.6232)	1600.893*** (372.1984)
Number of children under 10 years	13.60276 (195.6657)	289.8333 (232.1799)	772.7546*** (272.9789)	-675.147** (302.4921)	-253.904 (205.829)	-144.547 (265.859)
Age	439.9497*** (128.9571)	239.1021* (140.4946)	482.7963*** (156.6366)	-580.461*** (194.8171)	-98.5215 (142.6498)	30.46768 (184.8254)
Age-Square	-6.68303*** (1.752094)	-3.03097* (1.79011)	-5.51565*** (1.984121)	8.843205*** (2.650891)	2.700461 (1.96268)	1.227798 (2.694186)
Bank account dummy	1440.303*** (399.5092)	2178.798*** (385.9524)	2263.217 (378.4149)***	161.6799 (542.2534)	-84.5096 (391.6773)	793.3523 (497.0048)
Years of schooling	90.26607** (42.14)	196.6528*** (44.6199)	141.6484*** (52.30653)	-126.416 (58.09447)**	-63.2127 (39.67982)	-51.2932 (55.82447)
Constant	-878.049 (2292.133)	888.0155 (2723.783)	-2621.24 (3071.876)	9422.222 (3526.285)	2706.483 (2546.605)	1599.845 (3046.801)
Estimated quartile	6874.9	8599.5	10731	1601.3	3757.5	5755.2
Number of Observations	504	504	504	504	504	504
F(7, 496)	9.09	13.29	9.94	16.46	21.10	13.14
Prob > F	0.000	0.000	0.0000	0.0000	0.000	0.000
R-squared	0.1515	0.1378	0.0918	0.1588	0.1969	0.1207
Root MSE	3167.1	3403.2	4159	4034	2946.7	4130.6

Source: Authors' estimation based on the survey data. Note: *** p < .01; ** p < .05; *p < .1.

Figure 2. Distribution of pre-pandemic and post-pandemic income levels for male and female respondents based on unconditional quantile regression among slum dwellers in Kolkata, India. *Source:* Authors' drawing based on estimates from unconditional quantile regressions. (Regression results are available upon request from the authors)

Figure 2 most interestingly shows that, for male respondents, the income distribution curve for pre-pandemic period is slightly higher than that of the post-pandemic period. This indicates that male respondents may be still struggling to get back to their pre-pandemic income level. In our survey we observe that male respondents are mostly employed in the unorganised informal sector as drivers, taxi-drivers, auto-drivers, shop-owners, security guards, electricians, masons, house painters, catering services, cooks, sales men and delivery-partners, office bearers. During the lockdown period they were mainly out of job as shown by various studies (Dang et al. 2021; Kesar et al. 2021; Choudhuri et al. 2023). Our study further indicates that they are still coping with the shock of the pandemic. At this point, considering the female income distribution gives a different picture, as their post-pandemic income distribution is slightly higher than the pre-pandemic level. If we look at the pre- and post- pandemic employment status of male and female samples, as shown in Table 5, we can see that some females who were previously unemployed are now employed either full- or part-time. We observe that in our sample, females work mostly as domestic helpers, cooks, salespeople and other positions. Our results in Table 3 and Figure 1 show that total household income hardly changed in the pre- and post-pandemic periods. This may be due to the fact that a group of women who were previously unemployed has joined labour force to supplement their household income, as their husband or the breadwinner of the household are facing an income cut, even if it is statistically insignificant. In this respect, one male respondent commented that a cut in monthly income even as small as INR 300, causes a nutritional deprivation for their child, as the income cut prevents them from providing one egg per day to the child. This insecurity in livelihoods is compelling women to join the

labour force after the pandemic, as indicated by our case study. This result supports the observation made by the existing studies that there is a negative relationship between female labour force participation and household income or standard of living in the Indian context (Kapsos et al. 2014; Mehrotra and Parida 2017). The study by Mondal and Chakraborty (2022) also reported similar findings. A qualitative study based on samples from two towns in West Bengal observed that women who used to be home makers joined the labour force to supplement their household income after their husbands had lost their jobs during the pandemic.

Table 5. Employment status of male and female respondents residing in the slum area in Kolkata, India

Pre-Pandemic period			
Employment Status	Male	Female	Total
Unemployed	8	76	84
Full-time employed	236	107	343
Part-time employed	8	69	77
Total	252	252	504
Post-Pandemic period			
Unemployed	12	34	46
Full-time employed	230	124	354
Part-time employed	10	94	104
Total	252	252	504

Source: Authors' calculation

Next, we will analyse the determinants of employment status among individuals. Table 6 presents the results. In Table 6, the marginal effects of the multinomial probit model show that predicted probability of part-time employment is 5% higher in the post-pandemic period. Second, for female respondents, the predicted probability of full-time-employment is 42.75% lower, whereas the predicted probability of part-time employment is 27.89% higher, compared to male respondents. Thus, the multinomial probit regression results also indicate that in our case study, employment has slightly increased after the pandemic, and women are more likely to be employed as part-time workers in slum areas. This actually indicates traditional gender roles, where women are mostly responsible for all household chores and care activities, and after that they work part-time to supplement household income.

Next, we will analyse the determinants of time poverty. The table 7 shows the distribution of time across various activities by gender in the post-pandemic period.

The data clearly indicate a gender-specific discrimination in the distribution of time across activities. We observe that women are primarily engaged in caring for others and household activities, while male participates are mostly involved in market activities. Women spend 3 hours and 27 minutes more in household activities compared to men, while men spend 4 hours and 17 minutes more on paid work (market activity) than women. In India, taking care of children and elderly is mainly the responsibility of women. As a result, men have more time for leisure and sleeping than women.

Table 6. Results of multinomial probit regression on the determinants of employment status, with marginal effects for male and female respondents in the slums in Kolkata, India

Employment Status Categories	Coef. (Robust Std. Error)	Marginal Effects(dy/dx)* (Delta-method standard error)
1 (Unemployed) (base outcome)		
2 (Full-time employed)		
Covid dummy	.4523717*** (.1587476)	0.01961 (0.0240424)
Female dummy	-2.012533 *** (.1706181)	-0.4275*** (0.0183958)
BPL dummy	.7247501*** (.1629249)	0.12275*** (0.025293)
Number of children under 10 years	-.2621393** (.1163692)	-0.0204 (0.0188224)
Age	.184925** (.0749299)	0.035*** (0.0118354)
Age-square	-.0024528 ** (.0010286)	-0.0005*** (0.0001607)
Bank account dummy	.7303195*** (.2127843)	0.13895*** (0.0341393)
Constant	-.033379 (.0225397)	-0.0067** (0.0034002)
	-1.614585 (1.391743)	
3 (Part-time employed)		
Covid dummy	.6219006*** (.1699205)	0.05095** (0.0214623)
Female dummy	.3833179* (.2081851)	0.27891*** (0.0239127)
BPL dummy	.1508981 (.1746748)	-0.0541** (0.0235823)
Number of children under 10 years	-.2767572** (.1249396)	-0.0161 (0.0168749)
Age	.0044143 (.0774249)	-0.0193* (0.0102828)
Age-square	-.0000869 (.0010763)	0.00025* (0.0001408)
	.0107561 (.2134258)	-0.0772*** (0.0290438)

Employment Status Categories	Coef. (Robust Std. Error)	Marginal Effects(dy/dx)* (Delta-method standard error)
Bank account dummy	.0027208 (.0254572)	0.00404 (0.0032294)
Constant	-.3510996 (1.395613)	
Number of observations	1008	1008
Log pseudolikelihood		-649.30192
Wald chi2(16)		279.64***
AIC		1334.604
BIC		1423.087

Source: Authors’ estimation based on survey data. Note: *** p < .01; ** p < .05; *p < .1. AIC – Akaike’s information criterion; BIC – Bayesian information criterion

To determine how sensitive this result is to the employment status of men and women we have undertaken a sensitivity analysis. We identified that committed time of working women, which includes time spent on household activities, market activities and caring for others, is much higher than that of employed men.

Our sample household members failed to recall the time spent on various activities during the pre-COVID period, and therefore we were unable to measure how the distribution of time spent on these activities has changed after the pandemic. This is one of the study limitations. If we combine the changes in the distribution of employment status with the time spent by working individuals on committed activities, we can clearly see that the condition of employed women in terms of time left for leisure has worsened after the COVID-19 pandemic. Next, we examine the impact of gender on me-time left, while controlling for household size, age, age-square, number of children under 10 years, holding of a bank account, years of schooling and below poverty line (BPL) dummy (table 8).

We know that maintaining physical and mental health requires sufficient amount of sleep and leisure time. We refer to it as “me-time”. The table above shows the determinants of me-time in the overall sample and across different employment statuses. It has been identified that me-time is primarily determined by gender as well as by the variable indicating the number of children under 10 years. Me-time of fully employed and partially employed women is 48 minutes and 88 minutes less, respectively, than that of unemployed women. There is no significant difference in me-time among unemployed men and unemployed women. The number of children under 10 years significantly reduces me-time across all employment status subgroups.

Next, we have examined the incidence, depth and severity of time poverty, measured by committed time and me-time, across gender and employment status subgroups. Table 9 below reports the incidence, depth and severity of time poverty for each subgroup.

We observe that the overall sample incidence of time poverty is higher in men than in women, if we consider committed time to calculate time poverty. However, the incidence is lower in men when we take into account me-time to calculate time poverty. Depth and severity of time poverty is higher in men in both cases. When we break

Table 7. Gender gap in time spent in minutes on various activities among slum-dwellers in Kolkata, India, during the post-pandemic period

	Overall			Full Employment			Part-time Employment			Unemployment		
	Male	Female	Gender Gap	Male	Female	Gender Gap	Male	Female	Gender Gap	Male	Female	Gender Gap
Market activities	476.3 (10.2)	218.6 (9.1)	257.7*** (12.6)	502.2 (8.4)	315.2 (10.6)	186.9*** (13.8)	360 (48.2)	169.7 (7.3)	190.3*** (27)	0	0	0
Household activities	21.5 (1.9)	229.04 (3.01)	-207.6*** (3.6)	20.6 (1.7)	213.4 (3.2)	-192.7*** (3.3)	12 (3.9)	228.7 (3.6)	-216.7*** (11.2)	45 (23)	287.2 (12)	-242.2*** (24.3)
Care activities	63.3 (6.1)	114.7 (8.6)	-51.4*** (10.6)	62 (6.2)	72.3 (9.6)	-10.3 (11.0)	54 (28.9)	122.6 (12.2)	-68.6* (38.6)	95 (44.2)	247.3 (31.2)	-152.3 (59)**
Shopping	59.8 (1.9)	57.1 (2.1)	2.8 (2.8)	57.9 (1.9)	55.1 (2.8)	2.6 (3.2)	81 (7.8)	59.5 (3.02)	21.5** (9.6)	83.3 (13.8)	57.9 (8.6)	25.4 (16.6)
Travel	36.9 (1.8)	32.3 (1.4)	4.6** (2.2)	38.0 (1.8)	35.2 (1.6)	2.8 (2.7)	33 (10.9)	32.5 (2.2)	.47 (7.5)	18.3 (7.1)	20.9 (5.7)	-2.6 (10.5)
Sleeping	388.9 (3.6)	392.2 (3.5)	-3.2 (5.0)	387.5 (3.7)	375.5 (3.5)	12.03** (5.7)	402 (20.1)	392.6 (5.3)	9.4 (17.4)	405 (16.7)	451.8 (13.0)	-46.8* (24.1)
Personal care	101.3 (2.2)	143.0 (2.6)	-41.7*** (3.4)	96.2 (1.8)	129 (2.3)	-32.8*** (2.9)	127 (15.7)	150.1 (3.0)	-23.1** (10.4)	177.9 (14.9)	174.9 (13.3)	3 (24.1)
Leisure	290.3 (9.2)	253 (7.3)	37.2*** (11.5)	275.8 (8.3)	244.1 (9.3)	31.7** (13.2)	335 (43.2)	284.4 (12.3)	50.7 (40.1)	528.8 (80.5)	200 (20.9)	328.8*** (58.7)
Other	1.8 (1.5)	.12 (.12)	1.6 (1.5)	0	.24 (.24)	-.24 (.18)	36 (36)	0	36*** (11.3)	6.7 (6.7)	0	6.7* (3.9)
N	252	252		230	124		10	94		12	34	

Source: Authors' own calculation. Note: *** p < .01; ** p < .05; * p < .1.

down the sample by employment status, we see a different result. We observe that 25% of fully employed women are time poor, compared to only 8.3% of fully employed men. Depth and severity of time poverty based on committed time fall more heavily on fully employed women compared to men. This is probably an indication of an increase in time poverty among women compared to men during the post-COVID-19 period. Time poverty based on me-time falls more heavily on fully employed women than men. Unemployed women are more time poor than unemployed men in all respect. Thus, time poverty estimates vary across different subgroups. However, there is no doubt that the incidence and severity of time poverty is higher in women if they are full-time employed. This may be due to the prevailing social norm that household chores and care activities are mainly the responsibility of a wife, putting a significant time burden on fully employed women.

Table 8. Determinants of me-time by employment status among slum dwellers in Kolkata, India

	Overall Sample	Full Employment	Part-time Employment	Unemployment
Me-time	Coefficient (Robust Standard Error)			
Female dummy	-24.1** (10.6)	-48.1*** (12.0)	-81.8** (34.0)	-53.1 (85.5)
Age	-4.0 (5.3)	7.0 (5.4)	-13.3 (8.9)	-26.8 (19.9)
Age Square	.07 (.07)	-.07 (.07)	.16 (.12)	.41 (.28)
Number of children under 10 years	-63.1*** (8.4)	-53.6*** (9.2)	-106.6*** (16.7)	-95.2*** (27.3)
Bank account dummy	-30.2** (13.9)	-20.0 (14.0)	34.2 (22.5)	-85.2 (59.9)
Years of schooling	-4.0** (1.5)	-2.2 (1.7)	-5.0 (2.5)*	-13.9 (7.2)*
BPL dummy	7.4 (10.9)	15.5 (11.8)	24.7 (19.2)	60.2 (48.2)
Constant	798.5*** (98.6)	548.2*** (103.7)	1072.1*** (155.7)	1384.5 *** (363.4)
N	502	353	103	46
Adjusted R-Square	0.2293	0.2459	0.4293	0.6049

Source: Authors' own calculation. Note: *** p < .01; ** p < .05; * p < .1.

Table 9. Incidence, depth and severity of time poverty among slum-dwellers in Kolkata, India, during the post-pandemic period

	Time poverty measure	Committed time		Me-time	
		Female	Male	Female	Male
Overall sample	Incidence	0.1912	0.2430	0.0598	0.0438
	Depth	0.0186	0.0243	0.0034	0.0043
	Severity	0.0029	0.0040	0.0004	0.0006
Unemployed	Incidence	0.2647	0.2576	0.0806	0.0437
	Depth	0.0323	0.0258	0.0055	0.0042
	Severity	0.0051	0.0042	0.0007	0.0006
Part-time employed	Incidence	0.0860	0.1000	0.0108	0.0000
	Depth	0.0031	0.0167	0.0005	0.0000
	Severity	0.0003	0.0028	0.0000	0.0000
Full-time employed	Incidence	0.2500	0.0833	0.1176	0.0833
	Depth	0.0264	0.0035	0.0039	0.0101
	Severity	0.0042	0.0001	0.0002	0.0012
N		252	252	252	252

Source: Author's own calculation

Conclusion and policy recommendations

This study has analysed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the socioeconomic well-being of urban slum dwellers in Kolkata, focusing on income, employment, and time poverty. The study has identified two important facts: first, monthly household income did not change significantly during the pre- and post-COVID-19 periods, even though there was a slight decrease in the income of male slum dwellers, who are the main family breadwinner, during the post-pandemic period. Second, full-time and part-time employment of women increased during the post-COVID-19 period, compared to the pre-COVID-19 era, since women who used to be unemployed prior to the pandemic, joined the labour force to maintain their monthly household income. This shift reflects a fundamental change in the household economic dynamics, placing an increased financial and time burden on women.

We then have investigated whether there was any impact of employment status on time distribution among males and females in the post COVID-19 era and observed, that the incidence of time poverty was higher in full-time employed women compared to men. Gender and the number of children under 10 years in a household have been identified as an important determinant of me-time. Women have less me-time than men, and the number of children in the house significantly reduces me-time. This observation corroborates the standard finding that in Indian households, the traditional societal norm is that women take on the responsibility for household chores and caring for others, even when they are engaged in market activities. The reduced me-time experienced by women underscores a critical need for policy interventions focusing on equal distribution of household responsibilities and improved work-life balance.

The study results have strong policy implications. The findings clearly indicate the need for future employment policies in the informal sector, including social security measures, so that informal labourers and self-employed can more easily smooth out income shocks, such as the COVID-pandemic, in the long run. To address vulnerability of informal workers, the government of India needs to extend legal protection to these workers to ensure their rights. A focus group discussion on slum areas has identified difficulties faced by these people during the lockdown period, such as maintaining social distancing when using shared toilets and shared baths. The pandemic has taught us the importance of developing proper housing for the urban poor in slum areas. We strongly believe that this should become a priority for government policies.

We recommend a multi-pronged approach to address the challenges identified in this study:

First, to expand social safety nets and income support programs to informal workers to help them better cope with future economic downturns. This could include unemployment insurance, access to affordable health care, and readily available essential services. Additionally, robust legal protections for these workers would be also vital.

Second, to promote a more equitable distribution of household responsibilities. This requires a two-pronged strategy: (i) public awareness campaigns to challenge traditional gender roles and encourage shared responsibility for household chores and childcare; and (ii) development of community-based support systems, specifically designed to assist working women.

Third, to invest in improving the infrastructure in slum areas. Upgrading housing and sanitation will directly reduce the time costs associated with daily life for working women, and improve their overall well-being.

Fourth, to enhance women's mobility and free up valuable time, we propose a program of subsidized bicycle provision for working women in the informal sector. A phased implementation is recommended, ensuring community involvement, comprehensive safety training, and readily accessible maintenance and repair services.

Finally, continuous monitoring and further research are essential in order to track the long-term impacts of policies implemented, and make necessary adjustments. Future research should focus on gathering more detailed data on how time poverty impacts various demographic groups within the slum communities.

The limitations of this study – namely the inability to compare time poverty levels during the pre- and post-pandemic periods due to data constraints – highlight areas for future research that could improve our understanding of the long-term effects of the pandemic and the effectiveness of these interventions.

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